

Absorption of the Halogens by Mercurous Salts.

Part I.

Formation and Properties of some Complex Compounds of Mercury.

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The work undertaken (a preliminary note on which appeared in J. Amer. C. S., Vol. 45 (notes), pp. 2769-70) originated during the course of a mercurial preparation involving the use of calomel for outside application in which it was thought advisable to use iodine, as it was expected that (1) calomel would combine with iodine to form a compound with increased mercurial activity and (2) the iodine being a germicide would contribute favourably to the germicidal properties of the preparation.

The toxicity of mercuric salts is directly related to the ionising capacity of the salts, whilst mercurous salts like calomel, which are insoluble, cannot be absorbed to the necessary extent, and so their use as germicides is limited. It appeared, therefore, that if some way could be found to slightly increase the solubility of these compounds, without very much increasing their degree of dissociation, their usefulness would be greatly enhanced.

In the work described here the mercurous salts, chloride, sulphate and nitrate were shaken with alcoholic solutions of bromine and iodine. The latter were rapidly

absorbed and gave beautiful crystalline compounds from which attempts were made to produce the corresponding chloro-derivatives by passing dry chlorine gas over them. During the course of this work the following compounds were obtained:—

From mercurous chloride—

From mercurous sulphate—

From mercurous nitrate—

Compound (1) has been prepared by Kohler (B. 12, 1187) and by others but in small yield, whilst the method described here is extremely simple and gives quantitative yields of the pure product.

The fact that compound (5) was soluble in boiling water and it was found possible to estimate its bromine quantitatively in the ordinary way as silver bromide from its aqueous solution, as well as the fact that (6), which is derived from (5) by passing chlorine gas over it, is also soluble in water and in which chlorine could be estimated in the usual way, excludes the possibility of such compounds being molecular compounds or double salts having the formulæ $\text{HgSO}_4 \cdot \text{Hg Br}_2$, Br_2 and $\text{HgSO}_4 \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$. For it is well known that under such circumstances mercuric sulphate (and mercuric nitrate as well) would hydrolyse to a basic mercuric salt which will precipitate as a yellow substance. Hence the

mercury atom in such compounds can be suggested to form a part of the molecular complex, which would perhaps render such a preparation therapeutically useful.

The interaction of mercurous nitrate with the halogens gave tetrahalogen derivatives (7), (8) and (9). The bromo- and the chloro- derivatives (8) and (9), like (5), were soluble in a large quantity of boiling water without any hydrolysis and it was from the water solutions that the halogens were estimated in the usual way, confirming the view that all these compounds are not double salts but complex compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

(1) *Mercuric Chloriodide*

Two grams of powdered calomel were shaken with an alcoholic solution of iodine in a stoppered bottle at room temperature. The iodine began to be rapidly absorbed. After the absorption of the iodine ceased, the solution was kept for some days and a beautiful red crystalline compound was obtained. It was re-crystallised from alcohol. It changed from red to yellow at 125° and melted to a yellow liquid at 153°. Yield three grams.

(Found : Cl=9.58; I=35.22. HgClI requires Cl=9.79; I=35.03 per cent.)

The compound, though insoluble in water, dissolved readily in alcohol.

(2) *Mercuricchlorbromide*

Four grams of finely powdered calomel were shaken with an alcoholic solution of bromine as before, when the bromine was found to be rapidly absorbed with rise of temperature. The reaction mixture was consequently kept at room temperature by slightly cooling it under the tap. When bromine ceased to be absorbed, the

solution was allowed to evaporate to remove the excess of bromine, when a syrupy liquid was obtained which yielded a white crystalline mass on standing over sulphuric acid in a desiccator. It slowly sublimes without melting, when heated in a melting point tube. (Found: Cl = 11.23; Br = 24.98. HgClBr requires Cl = 11.26; Br = 25.36 per cent.)

The compound was freely soluble in alcohol, sparingly soluble in cold water, and easily soluble in boiling water.

When its solution in water is treated with silver nitrate, silver bromide is quantitatively precipitated.

On passing dry chlorine over mercuric chloriodide (1), at room temperature in a tube open at both ends, and driving away the excess chlorine by means of dry carbon dioxide, a white mass was obtained which when crystallised from alcohol was found to be identical with mercuric chloride (HgCl_2).

(4) *Di-iodo-dimercuric sulphate*

This compound was obtained as a red crystalline mass by shaking mercurous sulphate with an alcoholic solution of iodine under the conditions stated above. When crystallised from alcohol it turned yellow at 143° and melted at 248° . Yield quantitative.

(Found: I = 33.87. $\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4\text{I}_2$ requires I = 33.86 per cent.)

The compound though insoluble in water was soluble in alcohol.

(5) *Tetrabromodimercuric sulphate*

On treating mercurous sulphate with an alcoholic solution of bromine, under the conditions already described, a syrupy liquid was obtained, which deposited a white crystalline mass when left to crystallise in a desiccator over sulphuric acid. On recrystallisation from

alcohol, it was found to decompose at 125° and melt with decomposition at 235°.

(Found: Br=39·17; Hg=49·10; SO₄=11·78. Hg₂SO₄Br₂ requires Br=39·21; Hg=49·03; SO₄=11·77 per cent.)

The compound was found to be sparingly soluble in cold water, more in boiling water. It dissolved freely in alcohol. When allowed to stand in air it slowly emitted vapours of bromine. Silver bromide was quantitatively precipitated from its solution in water by the addition of silver nitrate.

(6) *Di-chlorodimercuric sulphate*

When dry chlorine gas was passed over (5) tetrabromodimercuric sulphate, a white amorphous mass was obtained which when crystallised from alcohol began to darken at 175° and melted at 270°.

(Found: Cl=12·50. Hg₂SO₄Cl₂ requires Cl=12·52 per cent.)

It is sparingly soluble in cold water, more in hot water and freely soluble in alcohol. Its halogen was estimated in the usual way from its water solution.

(7) *Tetraiododimercuric nitrate*

Mercurous nitrate was shaken with an alcoholic solution of iodine, as before. The resulting red compound was crystallised from alcohol, when it changed to yellow at 145-146° and melted at 250°. Yield quantitative.

(Found: I=49·22. Hg₂(NO₃)₂I₄ requires I=49·23 per cent.)

(8) *Tetrabromodimercuric nitrate*

This compound was prepared in the same way, as its corresponding iodo derivative, using an alcoholic solution of bromine in place of iodine. The resulting liquid, after the excess of bromine was allowed to go away, gave on

standing over sulphuric acid in a desiccator, a white crystalline substance which on subsequent re-crystallisation from alcohol, yielded a compound which decomposed on heating.

(Found: Br=38.02. $\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{Br}_4$ requires Br=37.91 per cent.)

The compound was very soluble in alcohol, appreciably soluble in cold water and more in hot water without decomposition. The halogen was estimated in the usual way from its water solution.

(9) *Tetrachlorodimercuricnitrate*

The above compound was obtained as a white amorphous powder, when dry chlorine gas was passed over (7) the corresponding tetraiodo compound. On crystallisation from alcohol it begins to decompose and darken at 100°. Yield quantitative.

(Found: Cl=21.16. $\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{Cl}_4$ requires Cl=21.32 per cent.)

The compound was sparingly soluble in cold water, more in boiling water and freely soluble in alcohol. The halogen could be quantitatively precipitated from its water solution by silver nitrate.

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FIG. 1